

Evaluation of the Effects of *Arachis hypogaea* and 5-Fluorouracil on Biochemical and Histological Parameters in 1,2-Dimethylhydrazine-Induced Colon Carcinogenesis in Mice

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Abstract

The established link between environmental and lifestyle factors and colorectal cancer necessitates continuous investigation into potential chemopreventive agents. This study evaluated the effect of *Arachis hypogaea* seeds and a standard drug, 5-fluorouracil, on the biochemical and histological parameters in 1,2-dimethylhydrazine-induced colon carcinogenesis in mice (*Mus musculus*). Twenty-eight mice used for this study were divided into seven groups of 4 mice each. 1, 2-dimethylhydrazine (DMH) was administered subcutaneously at a dose of 25 mg/kg body weight, and peanut was incorporated into the diet at a 20% level. Group 1 (control) mice were maintained on normal feed. Group 2 and 3 mice were maintained on normal feed and administered DMH once weekly for 12 and 6 weeks, respectively. Group 4 mice were administered DMH and a peanut-supplemented diet for 12 weeks. Group 5 mice received DMH weekly and a normal diet for the first 6 weeks, and a peanut-supplemented diet for the next 6 weeks. Group 6 mice were administered DMH and 5-fluorouracil for 12 weeks. Group 7 mice were maintained on only a peanut-supplemented diet for 6 weeks before being administered DMH. Results showed that DMH significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) elevated malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in colon tissue (1.38 ± 0.54 nmol/mg), which was reduced significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) by peanut supplementation and 5-fluorouracil treatment. Notably, Group 7 exhibited the lowest MDA levels (0.05 ± 0.03 nmol/mg). DMH administration also significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) decreased antioxidant enzyme activities and glutathione levels, which were reversed by peanut supplementation. Histological analysis confirmed carcinogenic alterations in the colonic mucosa of DMH-treated mice, while a peanut-supplemented diet mitigated these changes. These findings suggest that *Arachis hypogaea* seeds exert a protective, anticarcinogenic effect against DMH-induced colon carcinogenesis, supporting their potential as a dietary chemopreventive agent.

Keywords: 1,2-dimethylhydrazine, antioxidant enzymes, *Arachis hypogaea*, colon carcinogenesis, oxidative stress

1.0 Introduction

Cancer is a leading cause of illness and death globally [1]. It involves the abnormal and uncontrolled growth of cells, which can become malignant and result in a significant number of deaths each year [1]. Colorectal cancer, a common type of cancer affecting the colon and rectum, represents one of the leading causes of cancer-related morbidity and mortality worldwide, highlighting its significant contribution to the global cancer burden [2]. More than 90% of cancers are directly attributable to environmental and lifestyle factors,

making them largely preventable [3]. Colorectal cancer arises from a combination of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors, including inherited mutations, chronic inflammation [4], diets high in red or processed meats [5], physical activity [6], and excessive alcohol consumption [7]. These factors contribute to the accumulation of genetic and epigenetic changes that drive the development and progression of malignant tumors in the colon and rectum.

Cancer cell metabolism exhibits functional overlap with normal host cell metabolism, so effective cancer

treatment is highly challenging [8,9]. Designing drugs or therapeutics mainly focuses on selectivity, which can specifically kill the cancerous cells without affecting the non-cancerous cells. In numerous cases of localized cancer, administering chemotherapy before or after surgery or alongside radiotherapy can significantly enhance long-term survival outcomes. However, in the context of metastatic solid tumors, chemotherapy rarely leads to complete and lasting remission, with most treatment outcomes being limited to partial responses [10].

Many patients diagnosed with cancer receive some form of chemotherapy, with or without additional treatment. Potentially life-threatening side effects are associated with chemotherapy [11]. Therefore, mitigating chemotherapy-induced toxicity is essential for enhancing therapeutic efficacy and improving quality of life. Chemotoxicity arises from systemic DNA damage and inflammation in healthy cells due to chemotherapy drugs [11]. The clinical spectrum of toxicities is broad, ranging from less severe toxicities, such as nausea, vomiting, dysgeusia, and hair loss, to those that are more serious and potentially life-threatening which includes myelosuppression, febrile neutropenia, severe oral mucositis, and sepsis [12,13]. 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) is a main component of most chemotherapeutic regimens whose efficiencies have been established in the treatment of several neoplasms. The cytotoxic effect of 5-FU is mainly induced through inhibition of cellular thymidylate synthase (TS), leading to the prevention of DNA replication and also inhibition of RNA synthesis by the integration of its metabolites into RNA after intracellular activation [14]. Treatment with 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) is known to improve survival in various cancers. The largest impact of the drug has been reported in colorectal cancer [15].

The multifaceted interplay of genetic predisposition and environmental exposures in disease onset and progression has prompted in-depth research to uncover modifiable elements capable of decreasing incidence and improving prognosis. Diet and nutrition, essential part of human survival and important determinant of overall health are fundamental with a significant potential for influence and effect in the reduction of risk of cancers [16]. Extensive research has demonstrated that diet plays a role in cancer pathogenesis at the genetic, epigenetic and cellular level [16].

Peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea*) belong to the legume family and are grown in different parts of the world. It is grown mainly in Georgia, China, India, the United States of America, Nigeria, Indonesia, Argentina, and in low amounts in Turkey [17,18]. *Arachis hypogaea* is an important crop that contributes to food security and poverty reduction [19,20]. It can contribute to household food security as an important part of diets throughout Africa, supplying 32 different proteins, healthy fats, vitamins and essential minerals [21,22]. *Arachis hypogaea*, commonly known as peanut, contains a rich profile of dietary fiber, healthy fats, and various bioactive constituents such as flavonoids, stilbenoids, and phenolic acids, all associated with potential anticancer benefits. Given that colorectal cancer has a strong dietary component in its development, and considering the essential roles of the antioxidant system and histopathology in cancer diagnosis and treatment (23,24), this study was designed to investigate whether a diet enriched with peanut seeds could help prevent early cancer-related structural alterations in the colon of induced mice.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Source of plant material and preparation

Arachis hypogaea seeds were purchased at Uselu Market in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria in October, 2023. The identification of the peanut seed and plant was carried out by Prof. Henry A. Akinnibosun of the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, University of Benin. The *Arachis hypogaea* plant was assigned a voucher number UBHA352 and specimen deposited at the herbarium section of the department. The peanut seeds were sorted, cleaned and air dried for 48 hours. The raw seeds were ground to fine coarse powder in an electric blender (Sonik, model SB-566, Japan) and stored in air-tight containers in the refrigerator at 4°C.

2.2 Mice diet formulation

The peanut was incorporated into the rat diet at 20% level i.e., 20 g of peanut powder to 80 g of rat feed [25].

2.3 Source of experimental Animals

A total of twenty-eight (28) healthy male Wistar albino mice (*Mus Musculus*) were used for this study. They were purchased from the Department of Biochemistry, Animal Unit, Faculty of Life

Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria in October, 2023. They were housed in wood framed/iron meshed cages in the same facility. The mice were acclimatized for 2 weeks with unlimited access to water and feed (growers mash, product of Bendel Feeds and Flour Mills Limited, Ewu, Edo State, Nigeria) before the experiment commenced.

2.4 Preparation of 1, 2- dimethylhydrazine dihydrochloride (DMH)

Solution Stock 1- 2-dimethylhydrazine dihydrochloride 98% (DMH) (Sigma Aldrich, Germany) was dissolved in 1 mM ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA-saline) - saline solution just before use at a pH of 6.5, which was adjusted with 1 M NaOH to ensure that the carcinogen is stable at the time of use

2.5 Experimentation

The mice were divided into 7 experimental groups (Group 1 – Group 7) of 4 male rats each. DMH was administered at a dose of 25 mg/kg body weight subcutaneously [26]. Mice in each group were housed separately in a clean, disinfected cage in a room. Group 1 (G1) served as the control group. Mice in this group were maintained on the normal diet, growers mash, and the peanut-supplemented normal diet described above, and water *ad libitum*. Group 2 (G2) was treated with normal rat feed and subcutaneous injection of DMH 25 mg/kg body weight once weekly for 12 consecutive weeks. Group 3 (G3) was treated with normal feed and subcutaneous injection of DMH 25 mg/kg body weight once weekly for 6 consecutive weeks, and mice were provided with normal feed and water only for the next 6 weeks. Group 4 (G4) was injected with 25 mg DMH/kg body weight and the peanut-compounded diet (20% level) concomitantly for 12 weeks. Group 5 (G5) was treated with 25 mg DMH/kg body weight and normal feed for 6 weeks prior to a peanut-supplemented diet for the next 6 weeks. Group 6 (G6) was administered subcutaneous injection of 25 mg DMH/kg body weight and intraperitoneal injection of 5-fluorouracil (at a dose of 25mg/kg body weight in a volume of 1ml/kg using a solution concentration of 25mg/ml) concomitantly for 12 weeks. Group 7 (G7) was administered the peanut-incorporated diet for 6 weeks before the concomitant administration of 25 mg DMH/kg body weight and the peanut-incorporated diet (20% level) for 6 weeks.

2.7 Sample collection, preparation, and analyses

The study was carried out with strict compliance with the ethics in Guidelines and Specifications on Experimental Animal Care of Life Sciences, University of Benin (FLSRE-2023-010). Mice in each group were sedated in a halothane-saturated chamber. While under anesthesia, the colons were excised and homogenized by grinding 1 g portions in an ice-cold mortar with acid-washed sand in 5 mL physiological saline. The homogenates were subjected to centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes, and a clear supernatant was obtained which was kept at -20°C until required for biochemical analysis. Colons were also taken for histological analysis using standard laboratory procedures in the Department of Morbid Anatomy and Histopathology, UBTH, Benin. Preparation of colon sections was carried out by the method described by Kiernan [27].

2.8 Biochemical Assays

Malondialdehyde levels were measured based on its reaction with 2- thiobarbituric acid as described by Buege and Aust [28]. The method of Tietz [29] was used to determine the level of reduced glutathione. Reduced glutathione analysis was based on the ability of 5, 5 dithiobis (2- nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB) to undergo a reduction process in the presence of reduced glutathione (GSH) resulting in the production of a yellow compound. The reduced chromogen is directly proportional to the concentration of GSH. Superoxide dismutase activity was assessed by the method of Misra and Fridovich [30] which involved following the auto-oxidation of adrenaline to adrenochrome at 420 nm. Catalase activity was examined by the method of Cohen et al. [31], in which the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide was monitored at 480 nm.

2.9 Data analysis

The data obtained from the biochemical assays were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). In order to establish whether the mean values were statistically significantly different from each other, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was done using SPSS software (Version 21.0). To know which means have differences that are significantly different, an LSD multiple range test was done by employing the same SPSS computer software. Values were considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

3.0 Results

3.1 Effect of 1,2-Dimethylhydrazine in the Colon of Mice Fed with *Arachis hypogea* Compounded Diet

The result shown in Table 1 revealed that twelve weeks of subcutaneous induction of DMH significantly ($p < 0.05$) elevated the MDA concentration (1.38 ± 0.54^b) relative to the normal control (0.34 ± 0.26^a). Consequently, the activity of colon antioxidant enzymes was significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced following the induction of DMH for twelve weeks relative to the normal control. On a six-week induction of DMH, concentration of MDA (1.27 ± 0.99^c) was significantly ($p < 0.05$) elevated relative to the normal control (0.34 ± 0.26^a), but not as much as the twelve-week induction. However, the activity of colon antioxidant enzymes was

significantly reduced in the group induced with DMH relative to the normal control ($p < 0.05$). A single dose induction of DMH, followed by twelve weeks of exposure to a compounded diet, exhibited a modulation in the elevation of MDA concentration relative to the normal control ($p > 0.05$) and DMH (12 weeks) group ($p < 0.05$). A similar modulatory response was observed in the activities of colon antioxidant enzymes in groups exposed to *Arachis hypogea* compounded diet for twelve weeks after a single dose intraperitoneal induction of DMH, when compared with the normal control ($p > 0.05$) and DMH (12 weeks) group ($p < 0.05$). The characteristic response of the colons of mice exposed to the compounded diet for both twelve (12) and six (6) weeks was in a similar order. This was also recorded for the group treated with fluorouracil (standard drug)

Table 1: Levels of 1,2-dimethylhydrazine in the colon of mice exposed to *Arachis hypogea* compounded diet

Groups	MDA (nmol/mg)	GPx(U/mg)	SOD(U/mg)	CAT(U/mg)
G1 (Control)	0.34 ± 0.26^a	1.05 ± 0.04^a	1.30 ± 0.10^a	1.34 ± 0.07^a
G2 (DMH 12wks)	1.38 ± 0.54^b	0.05 ± 0.03^b	0.11 ± 0.05^b	0.27 ± 0.04^b
G3 (DMH 6wks)	1.27 ± 0.99^c	0.05 ± 0.03^c	0.20 ± 0.10^c	0.31 ± 0.05^c
G4 (DMH + Diet 12WKS)	0.38 ± 0.20^a	0.78 ± 0.04^a	1.93 ± 0.02^a	1.21 ± 0.02^a
G5 (DMH 6wks + Diet 6wks)	0.30 ± 0.45^a	0.81 ± 0.11^a	1.77 ± 0.15^a	1.25 ± 0.02^a
G6 (DMH + Fluorouracil 12wks)	0.42 ± 0.45^a	0.97 ± 0.05^a	0.98 ± 0.04^a	1.22 ± 0.02^a
G7 (Diet 6wks + DMH + Diet 6wks)	0.05 ± 0.03^b	0.98 ± 0.02^a	0.79 ± 0.16^a	1.26 ± 0.00^a

Key: DMH = 1,2- Dimethylhydrazine; GPx = glutathione peroxidase; SOD = superoxide dismutase; CAT = catalase; MDA = malondialdehyde; GI = group 1; G2 = group 2; G3 = group 3; G4 = group 4; G5 = group 5; G6 = group 6; G7 = group 7. Values are represented as mean \pm SEM. Values in the same column with different alphabets (a or b) differ significantly ($p < 0.05$).

3.2 Histological Analysis

Figure 1 shows the results of the histopathological examination (Plates I–VII). Photomicrograph of colon section of control (plate I) reveals prominent histology with normal mucosal details bound by muscularis externa and distinct columnar epithelium and villi in the mucosa. Mice maintained on DMH for 12 weeks, group 2 (plate II), reveal many neoplastic crypts and glands irregular in shape and size, with a tendency to an exophytic growth. The photomicrograph also revealed that crypts are lined by a tall, hyperchromatic, somewhat disordered epithelium without differentiation into mature goblet cells. Marked fibrosis in the muscularis externa was also prominent. Subcutaneous injection of DMH for 6 weeks (plate III) reveals visible neoplastic crypts and glands with irregular shapes and sizes. The

crypts are lined by a tall, hyperchromatic, and slightly disordered. The submucosa and muscularis externa appear loose and thin. Colon histology of group 4 mice, where *Arachis hypogaea* seeds powder was used to supplement the diet (plate IV), reveals visible histology with prominent mucosal details bound by muscularis externa, columnar epithelium, and villi in the mucosa, which revealed mild visible proliferating changes.

Photomicrograph of colon section of group 5 (plate V) reveals visible histology with prominent mucosal details bound by thick muscularis externa and columnar epithelium and villi in the mucosal layer, revealing mild visible proliferating changes. Photomicrograph of colon section of group 6 administered DMH and fluorouracil (standard drug) (plate VI) reveals histology with mucosal details

bound by muscularis externa. The submucosa showed infiltrates with mononuclear exudates, visible columnar epithelium, and elongated villi in the mucosa, with visible crypts of Lieberkühn and goblet cells, exhibiting mild apoptosis. Photomicrograph of colon section of group 7 mice

that received supplemented diet before DMH administration (plate VII) reveals normal columnar histoarchitecture with mucosal details bound by muscularis externa (long arrow) and columnar epithelium and villi in the mucosa with abundant crypts of Lieberkühn and goblet cells.

Figure 1: Photomicrograph showing the colon histologic section of mice of control, DMH, and *Arachis hypogaea* treated groups (H&E $\times 100$)

Photomicrograph of colon section of control (plate I): Normal mucosal details bound by muscularis externa (long arrow) and distinct columnar epithelium and villi in the mucosa (short arrow).

Photomicrograph of colon section of group 2 (plate II): neoplastic crypts and glands (short arrow), marked fibrosis in muscularis externa (long arrow).

Photomicrograph of colon section of group 3 (plate III): neoplastic crypts and (short arrow), the sub-mucosa and muscularis externa appear loose and thin (long arrow).

Photomicrograph of colon section of group 4 (plate IV): visible histology with prominent mucosal details bound by muscularis externa (long arrow), and columnar epithelium, mild visible proliferating changes in the mucosa (short arrow).

Photomicrograph of colon section of group 5 (plate V): visible histology with prominent mucosal details bound by thick muscularis externa (long arrow) and columnar epithelium and villi in the mucosa revealing mild visible proliferating changes (short arrow).

Photomicrograph of colon section of group 6 (plate VI): mucosal details bound by muscularis externa (long arrow), sub-mucosa infiltrated with mononuclear exudates (arrow head), visible columnar epithelium and elongated villi in the mucosa with visible crypt of Lieberkühn and goblet cells showing mild apoptotic changes (short arrow).

Photomicrograph of colon section of group 7 (plate VII): normal colon histology with mucosal details bound by muscularis externa (long arrow) and columnar epithelium and villi in the mucosa with abundant crypts of Lieberkühn and goblet cells (short arrow).

4.0 Discussion

In this study, a significant increase in MDA showed evidence of lipid peroxidation in the colon tissue in mice treated with DMH for 12 weeks and 6 weeks, respectively (groups 2 and 3) relative to the control. Mice treated with DMH for only 6 weeks still showed MDA-induced oxidative stress after 12 weeks. This shows the effective potential of DMH in the induction of oxidative stress [32,33] and oxidative stress associated with its role as a colon carcinogen [34,26]. Mice treated with DMH and peanut-incorporated diet showed a slight increase in MDA compared to the control, while Group 5 showed the same level of MDA compared to the control. This indicates that the peanut-incorporated diet was effective in reducing lipid peroxidation caused by DMH. This is in agreement with findings by Isoje and Obi on the ameliorative effect of *Arachis hypogaea* seed powder on DMH-induced oxidative stress in exposed rats [26]. Group 6 (mice treated with DMH and 5-fluorouracil simultaneously for 12 weeks) showed decreased MDA compared to the DMH-induced mice (groups 2 and 3), though higher than the control (group 1), indicating its positive effect as a chemotherapeutic drug in ameliorating the effect caused by DMH-induced damage. However, when compared with mice treated with a peanut-incorporated diet, the peanut-incorporated diet was more effective in reducing lipid peroxidation. The efficacy of the peanut-incorporated diet in preventing and mitigating chemically induced carcinogenesis may be due to the action of several phytochemicals, notably phenolic compounds present in the peanuts (35). Polyphenols are believed to have the capacity to induce the expression of enzymes that can enhance the detoxification of xenobiotics although the mechanism remains unclear [36].

Data from this study showed a considerable depletion in all the antioxidant enzyme activities in the group of mice exposed to DMH alone (groups 2 and 3) compared to the control (group 1). Mice treated with peanut-incorporated diet and 5-fluorouracil (Group 4, 5, 6, 7) showed reduced antioxidant activities (GPx, SOD and CAT) compared to the control but more elevated activities compared to mice treated with DMH only. The ameliorative effect of peanut-incorporated diet and the general lowering of MDA levels indicate that peanuts have antioxidant potency. This study also revealed that a 20% peanut-incorporated diet is as effective as 5-fluorouracil in its ameliorative

potency. This study agrees with findings by Isoje and Obi [26] on the ameliorative effect of peanut-incorporated diet in DMH-treated rats. This could be attributed to the bioactive components (phenolic compounds, stilbenes, lignans, and isoflavonoids) in its composition, which help alleviate oxidative damage and inflammatory response triggered by reactive oxygen species [35,37].

Neoplastic crypts (an abnormal, cancerous growth originating from the colonic crypt), irregular shapes and sizes with tendency to an exophytic growth, tall, hyperchromatic and disordered epithelium without differentiation into goblet cells, fibrosis in muscularis from the histological study indicates preneoplastic lesions in DMH-induced colon carcinogenesis as seen in mice exposed to DMH for 12 weeks and 6 weeks (plate II and III). This is in agreement with previous studies by Petras and Frankel [38] that carcinoma of the right colon tends to produce large exophytic growth. Isoje *et al.* [24] also reported that administration of DMH to Wistar rats induced varying degrees of dysplasia in the colonic mucosal epithelial lining and crypts. The presence of fibrosis in the muscularis mucosae indicates an inflammatory response associated with tumor progression. This is usually characterized by the infiltration of inflammatory cells, which can contribute to the development of adenocarcinomas [39]. These alterations are indicative of preneoplastic lesions that have the potential to progress to invasive colorectal cancer. Protective and ameliorative effects varied in extent (Plates IV, V, and VII). While post-DMH treatment with peanuts for 6 and 12 weeks resulted in only mild restoration of colonic histoarchitecture (Plates IV and V), pre-administration of a peanut-based diet before DMH administration (Plate VII) preserved near-normal colon histoarchitecture. This protective effect is likely due to bioactive phytochemicals in peanuts, as earlier opined by Isoje *et al.* [24]. Similarly, 5-fluorouracil, a standard used in colon cancer chemotherapy (Plate VI), also resulted in mild restoration of the colon histoarchitecture; however, the sub-mucosa was infiltrated with mononuclear exudates, indicating a chronic inflammatory response [40].

Arachis hypogaea ameliorated the effect of DMH in treated mice, especially when given prophylactically. Although *Arachis hypogaea* exhibited similar efficacy in mice that received intraperitoneal injection of 5-fluorouracil, it,

however, showed no histological evidence of colonic toxicity.

5.0 Conclusion

It is evident from this study that the incorporation of peanuts into the diet of rats exposed to DMH effectively mitigated and prevented oxidative stress in the colon of the mice. Findings from this study showed that the anticarcinogenic effect of a peanut-supplemented diet is as effective as the standard chemotherapeutic drug, 5-fluorouracil, but without any toxic side effects. This study, therefore, suggests that incorporating peanut into the diet of experimental animals ameliorated the DMH-induced oxidative stress and changes in colon histology. Importantly, a peanut-supplemented diet before DMH treatment effectively protects the colon from DMH-induced damage, showing its anticarcinogenic potential.

The future perspective of this study would be to explore the molecular mechanisms underlying the protective effects of *Arachis hypogaea*. Specifically, studies should investigate whether the diet exerts its effects through modulation of cellular signaling pathways such as the Nrf2/ARE pathway, which regulates the expression of detoxifying and antioxidant enzymes. Further examination of other key molecules involved in oxidative stress, inflammation, and apoptosis, such as HO-1, NF- κ B, and caspases. This would offer a clearer mechanistic understanding of how dietary components exert their chemopreventive effects.

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